

Modern Diagnosis and Treatment Technique of Chronic Rhinosinusitis

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Relevance of the experience: Chronic rhinosinusitis is characterized by a long duration and usually occurs without a significant increase in temperature. The acute condition is always accompanied by high fever, begins unexpectedly and has more pronounced painful symptoms. The main reason for the development of chronic inflammation of the maxillary sinuses is the violation of their normal drainage. It occurs due to long-term infectious or non-infectious swelling (allergy, drug-related swelling) or a violation of mucous membrane clearance in the area of the maxillary nasal anastomosis. Also, the background for the formation of chronic inflammation is anatomical obstacles in the nose that disrupt normal drainage (deviation of the septum, expansion of the middle turbinates).

Object of examination: long-term allergic swelling of the nasal mucosa;

frequent respiratory tract infections;

septal deformation;

hypertrophy of middle turbinates;

long-term swelling of a non-allergic nature (medicinal rhinitis);

chronic inflammatory process in the area of upper teeth (periodontitis, odontogenic cysts);

foreign bodies (filling material, sinus lifting material, tooth roots, etc.);

neoplasms in the nasal cavity or paranasal sinuses;

other diseases: cystic fibrosis, gastroesophageal reflux, HIV infection, immunodeficiency conditions.

Investigations: Rhinosinusitis is more likely to develop into a chronic form if one or more of the following factors are present:

smoking;

immune system disorder;

frequent contact with irritants (chemicals, smoke, suspension of small particles, dust, allergens).

Complications of chronic rhinosinusitis

Long-term inflammation poses many risks because the sinuses are located close to important structures such as the eyes and brain:

Examination methods: A flexible, soft tube (endoscope) with a fiberoptic light allows the doctor to see the nasal passages, the sinus area, and sometimes the inside of the sinuses.

x-ray tomography. Images from a computed tomography (CT) scan can show details of your maxillary sinuses and nasal area. The doctor determines the size and nature of the sinus lesions and evaluates the patency of the sinus-nasal connections.

Planting from the mucous layer for flora. It allows to determine the infectious cause of sinus inflammation (if any) (fungi, bacteria) and prescribe the necessary treatment.

Allergy test. If the doctor suspects that this condition is caused by an allergy, you should do an allergy test (rhinocytogram, blood IgE, eosinophil cationic protein).

Observed results: The goal of treatment is to reduce the number of sinusitis exacerbations and reduce or eliminate the symptoms of the disease. The main therapy is aimed at improving the drainage of the paranasal sinuses, as well as improving the local immunity of the mucous membranes. For this, it is necessary to remove the blockage of the sinus-nasal anastomosis, reduce the viscosity of the mucous secretion, and conduct immunotherapy. Sometimes surgery is required to clear the sinuses.

Conclusion: Surgical treatment of chronic rhinosinusitis with low effectiveness of conservative therapy is indicated. It is a mechanical obstacle to sinus drainage (enlarged turbinate, deformed nasal septum, anatomical narrowing of the sinus anastomotic area, polyp in the anastomotic area, etc.), as well as to protect the sinuses from foreign attachments (fungal bodies, tooth roots, filling material, sinus lifting material for), cysts, polyps. In cases where conservative treatment does not help, endoscopic surgery is performed. To perform this procedure, the doctor uses an endoscope (a thin tube with a video camera and light) to examine the nasal passages. In addition, depending on the nature of the obstruction, the doctor can use different instruments to remove tissue or destroy polyps that block the flow of contents from the paranasal sinuses. In the surgical treatment of the nasal cavity and sinuses, we follow Walter Messerklinger's concept (functional endonasal sinus surgery, FESS), which has become a whole surgical field in recent years. Functional endonasal (through the nose) microsurgery is based on the principle of soft surgical intervention in special areas. With this approach, only the affected or abnormally located tissue is removed with the help of a razor (microrazor) with maximum preservation of the "healthy" mucous membrane. The goal of surgical treatment with FESS surgery is to restore natural ventilation and drainage pathways (stomachs).

Avoid upper respiratory infections. Minimize contact with people who have a cold. Wash your hands often with soap, especially before eating.

Monitor and manage your allergies, if any.

Avoid smoky rooms and polluted air. Tobacco smoke and other pollutants can cause irritation and inflammation in the nasal passages and lungs.

Use humidifiers. If the air in your home is dry, for example, you have air heating, then using humidifiers can help prevent sinusitis. Keep the unit clean and free of mold.

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